

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

LINGUISTIC DEVIATION AND ACTUALIZATION

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Abstract

Linguistic deviations surround poetic forms based on individual creativity. In poetic language, grammatical anomalies allowed for specific purposes are not errors. There are no limitless linguistic deviations that do not fit into the framework. The role of semantics and human cognition is prominent in understanding the text, free from strict grammatical rules, which resonates with the views of anthropocentrism in linguistics.

Keywords: deviation, actualization, foreground, an abnormal regularity, poetry.

As an introduction to our article, we consider it helpful to consider as an example the first part of the poem "Ode to the West Wind" by the 19th century English poet Percy Bysshe Shelley, presented by J. Leach, and conduct our analysis on it.

Ode to the West Wind

*O wild West Wind, thou breath of Autumn's being
Thou, from whose unseen presence the leaves
dead*

Are driven, like ghosts from an enchanter fleeing,

*Yellow, and black, and pale, and hectic red,
Pestilence-stricken multitudes: O thou,
Who chariotest to their dark wintry bed*

*The wingèd seeds, where they lie cold and low,
Each like a corpse within its grave, until
Thine azure sister of the Spring shall blow*

*Her clarion o'er the dreaming earth, and fill
(Driving sweet buds like flocks to feed in air)
With living hues and odours plain and hill:*

*Wild Spirit, which art moving everywhere;
Destroyer and preserver; hear, oh, hear!* (Shelley)

Deviation determines the criteria for the selection of linguistic features of literary nature. The deviation is especially characteristic of poetic language. The poet goes beyond the "observed norms" of linguistic expression. In a broad sense, it exercises poetic license. Depending on the type of norm, the kind of deviation also changes. M. Mahlberg refers to J. Leach to justify this opinion and distinguishes first-order, second-order and third-order types of deviation [9, pp. 20-21].

There are two primary forms of first-degree deviation:

1) the poet goes beyond the usual range of choices;
2) the poet uses the same subject in successive positions, depriving himself of the right to choose.

In many cases, the first type of deviation corresponds to Jakobson's famous criterion of the poetic function of language: "The poetic function projects the principle of equivalence from the axis of selection to the axis of combination" [7, p.358].

The first type of deviation can easily explain in the following verses:

*Who chariotest to their dark wintry bed / The
winged seeds, where they lie cold and low*

Here we encounter a lexical deviation in the choice of the rarely used verb *chariotest*. On the other hand, a collocational deviation that is relatively accurately reflected in the standard form:

*The wind (adverb) chariots (verb) the seeds (com-
plete) to their bed (adverb)*

Here we can see a deviation related to the syntactic word order (hyperbaton - introduction and postponement) in the sequence of subject + verb news + adverb + complement, which can be considered abnormal for the grammatical rules of the English language. The shared strangeness of the wind carrying the seeds to bed provides the basis for a metaphor that personifies the wind and the seeds. Thus, standard deviation or inconsistent juxtaposition of words is the basis of semantic deviation, more precisely, poetic metaphor. We must be able to distinguish simile and metaphor. Aristotle said that the creation of good metaphors depends on understanding similarities in things [1, p.61].

A simple example of the second type of first-order deviance is the alliterative example *O wild West Wind* with which the poem begins. The poet chooses the same /w/ consonant in successive syllables. In this word-initial position, a large number of phonemes can find. But the poet focuses on only one of these phonemes in his choice: the example that catches the reader's or listener's attention. A more straightforward example at the lexical-syntactic level is the example of repeated structural choice in the first three stanzas. C. Leach shows it schematically as follows:

I O... Wind, O+Vocative
Thou breath..., Vocative + Appositive
Thou, from whose... Vocative + Relative Clause
O Thou, who chariotest... O + Vocative + Rela-
tive Clause
Wild Spirit, which... Vocative + Relative Clause
Destroyer Vocative
hear, oh, hear! Imperative + O + Imperative

II Thou on whose... Vocative + Relative Clause
Thou dirge... Vocative + Appositive

to which... + Relative Clause
 from whose... + Relative Clause
 Oh, hear! O + Imperative

III Thou who didst... Vocative + Relative Clause
 Thou for whose path... Vocative + Relative Clause
 oh, hear! O + Imperative

Although the model is incorrect, the above summary shows that the poet associates the change with only five structural elements: the exclamatory O, the vocative, the adjunct, the relative clause, and the imperative verb hear. Briefly, deviation exhibits either abnormal irregularity (hyperbaton) or abnormal regularity (syntactic parallelism and other types of schematic patterns). The form of verse (weight, rhyme, line) is an abnormal regularity.

Nevertheless, it is a set of schematic structures that allows its specific stylistic variation rather than a form of stylistic variation [8, p.56].

The foreground is a term the reader elicits through linguistic or other forms of deviance. Unexpected deviation draws the reader's attention to the foreground as a "deautomization" of normal language processes [14]. In his work, Jan Boas Beyer, referring to J. Leach, considered the foreground and deviation as "the key to the stylistic explanation of literature" [2, p.120]. Maryana Hundt includes foregrounding, deviation and parallelism in her discussion of stylistic concepts. The author noted that stylistics began in the 20th century with the ideas of Russian formalism and showed that it is closely related to the concepts of foreground and deviation. Based on John Douthwaite [4] and J. Leach's propositions, he writes that foregrounding is related to the process by which the individual features of the text are distinguished. Deviation includes one of these means, divided into internal and external deviation. External deviation refers to features that differ from language norms, and internal deviation does not differ from the norms manifested in the text [6, p. 675]. Foreground, or aktualisace in Czech, is understood as a deviation from the norm or norm. Stefano Cotrozzi claims that the term comes from the Prague school of linguistics, which was perfected by the Russian formalists. In a broader sense, this term is synonymous with emphasis, focus, or emphasis [3, p.1]. Foregrounding is related to linguistic mechanisms at all levels of language. It sets against the background of the text or contextual factors such as literary genre. Actualization is a relative concept compared to norms and established rules. They are associated with complex contextual cues. Deviation and parallelism can be examples of actualization [10 p. 95].

In addition to the normal processes of interpretation applied to a text, whether literary or not, actualization also characterizes creative interpretation by the reader. It is necessary to use the power of imagination to clarify the reasons for the existence of the unusual. In the case of poetic deviation, it would be appropriate to ask such a question: What does the poet mean by this? Specific communicative values of poetry are the basis of creative acts. John Strachan compares the real meaning with the figurative meaning and claims that the essence of figurative language in prose or poetry is

related to creating deviation or actualization [13, p. 111].

The communicative essence of deviation can be determined by its lower and upper standards. While the lower standard of deviation narrows the range of meaning, its upper standard covers a broader range of meaning [12, p. 139]. The deviations between the texts in each communicative sphere can be explained by various types [11, p.48].

According to Jeffrey Leach, communicative values can be explained in the following essential categories:

a) contrast, for example: (destroyer) and (preserver) from the mountain in line 14.

b) similarity; for example, the similarity is expressed through metaphor. In lines 6 and 7, the wind is likened to a coachman, the seeds to passengers, and the earth to a bed.

c) parallelism, for example, the lexical-syntactic parallelism of verses, is mentioned in the above poem.

So, 1) the force of the wind on the ground (terrestrial nature), 2) the force of the wind in the sky (aerial nature), and 3) the force of the wind in the sea (aquatic nature).

d) mimesis: Referring to Plato in his ideas, Aristotle interpreted the concept of mimesis in different ways. Although Aristotle approached this concept on an aesthetic level and limited it to poetry and music, in all cases, the meaning of the term "imitation" gained more priority [5, p.53]. The /w/ sounds at the beginning of the words in the phrase O wild West Wind in Shelley's poem and the hissing (sibilant) sounds in the following line (from whose unseen presence the leaves dead) can be shown as examples of onomatopoeia imitating the sound of the wind. Although some critics consider analogical concepts unimportant, one can agree with J. Leach that mimesis with an abstract and complex form has a vital role in the analysis of the meaning and structure of the poem.

References

1. Aristotle. Roberts R. Rhetoric. / Aristotle, R.Roberts. – New York: Cosimo, Inc., – 2010. – 194 p.
2. Boase-Beier J. A Critical Introduction to Translation Studies./J. Boase-Beier. – London: A&C Black, – 2011. – 200 p.
3. Cotrozzi S. Expect the Unexpected: Aspects of Pragmatic Foregrounding in Old Testament Narratives. / Cotrozzi S. – London: A&C Black, – 2010. – 290 p.
4. Douthwaite J. Towards a Linguistic Theory of Foregrounding. / J.Douthwaite. – Alessandria: Edizioni dell'Orso, – 2000. – 403 p.
5. Gebauer W. Ch. Mimesis: Culture Art Society. Translated by Don Reneau. /W.Ch. Gebauer. – London: University of California Press, – 1995. – 400p.
6. Hundt M. Change in Grammar / M.Hundt //The Oxford Handbook of English Grammar edited by B.Aarts, J.Bowie and G.Popova. / A.Hughes, P.Trudgill, D.Watt. – Oxford: Oxford University Press, –2019. – 864 p.
7. Jakobson R. Closing statement: linguistics and poetics / R. Jakobson. Ed. A. Sebeok Thomas (ed.)

Style in Language. – Cambridge: MIT Press, – 1960. – p. 350–377.

8. Leech, G. N. Language in literature: style and foregrounding / G.Leech – London and New York: Routledge, – 2013. – 183 p.

9. Malyuga E., Orlova S. Linguistic Pragmatics of Intercultural Professional and Business Communication / E.Malyuga, S.Orlova – Berlin: Springer, – 2017. – 145 p.

10. Nørgaard N., Busse B., Montoro R. Key Terms in Stylistics / N.Nørgaard, B.Busse, R.Montoro – London: A&C Black, – 2010. – 269 p.

11. Prague Studies in Mathematical Linguistics, Том 8. Eva Hajičová, Marie Těšitelová, Ján Horecký. Československá akademie věd. – Tuscaloosa: University of Alabama Press, – 1983 – 244 p.

12. Romanowski P. Intercultural Communicative Competence in English Language Teaching in Polish State Colleges / P. Romanowski – Cambridge: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, – 2017. – 205 p.

13. Strachan J. Poetry / J. Strachan – Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, – 2011. – 256 p.

14. Van Peer. Stylistics and Psychology: Investigations in Foregrounding / Van Peer – London: Croom Helm, – 1986. – 220 p.

MINOR HUMAN TRAGEDY IN THE NOVELS OF MIKHAIL NUAYMAN

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МАЛАЯ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКАЯ ТРАГЕДИЯ В РОМАНАХ МИХАИЛА НУАЙМАНА

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Abstract

Already in the first quarter of the 20th century, the novella genre had a special place in Arabic literature. Researchers give different answers to the question "who is the first in the creation and application of this genre?" Nuayma takes the first place in the short story genre, because it was he who was able to revive real life here. In his novellas, Nuayma describes the life of her compatriots, who are often victims of illiteracy and superstition. Harmful customs and traditions are sharply criticized. It exposes the inner face of ambitious and profit-seeking people and opposes women's rightslessness.

Аннотация

Уже в первой четверти 20 века жанр новеллы занимал особое место в арабской литературе. При создании и применении этого жанра исследователи дают разные ответы на вопрос, «кому принадлежит первое место». Нуайма занимает первое место в жанре новеллы, ведь именно он смог оживить здесь реальную жизнь. В своих новеллах Нуайма описывает жизнь соотечественников, которые часто становятся жертвами пошлости и суеверий. Вредные обычаи и традиции подвергаются резкой критике. Он обнажает внутреннее лицо амбициозных и корыстолюбивых людей и выступает против женского бесправия.

Keywords: Mikhail Nuayman, novella, little man, tragedy, idea

Ключевые слова: Михаил Нуайман, новелла, маленький человек, трагедия, идея

Nuayma's creativity is multifaceted. His talent manifests itself equally successfully in all genres. Besides, novellas occupy a special place among his works. The writer's novellas are distinguished by features such as brevity, simplicity of expression, accuracy in describing the surrounding reality, variety of characters, plot dynamics and readability, subtle lyricism, and psychological richness.

The study of Mikhail Nuayma's novellas provides valuable material for illuminating the main aspects of modern Arabic literature.

Already in the first quarter of the 20th century, the novella genre had a special place in Arabic literature. Researchers give different answers to the question of

"who is the first" in the creation and application of this genre. Some give the right of primacy to Muhammad Lutfi Juma: His collection of stories called "In the Houses of the People" ("Fi bûyt en-nas") was published in 1904. Muhammad Rushdu Hasan stands at the head of writers who confirm that the first place belongs to M. L. Jume. He confirms his point of view in his research devoted to the creation of a short story in Arabic literature [3, p.90].

Another group of researchers considers Muhammad Teymur (1892-1921), known mainly as a playwright, to be the founder of the Arabic novella. The writer's first story "On the Train" was published in 1917. In the same year, his collection of stories "What